

UTILIZATION OF CRISPR-CAS AS A GENOME EDITING TOOL TO
ENCODE THE NOTCH1-MNEONGREEN FUSION PROTEIN IN
MAMMALIAN CELLS

by

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Utilization of CRISPR-Cas as a Genome Editing Tool to Encode the Notch1-mNeonGreen Fusion Protein in Mammalian Cells

Abstract

Clustered regularly interspaced palindromic repeats (CRISPR-Cas) is an example of DNA editing technology that is naturally found in the immune system of bacteria but has been engineered to edit DNA sequences in mammalian cells. CRISPR-Cas can be used by medical scientists to treat genetic diseases like sickle cell anemia, which received approval from the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in 2023.³⁰ The popularity of using CRISPR-Cas has increased due to its ability to add/delete any DNA sequence into a specific site in the genome. This requires a guide RNA (target) sequence. The guide RNA chosen for this project was the Notch1 gene that encodes the Notch1 protein, which is part of the Notch signaling pathway vital for the embryonic development of tissues throughout the body. In this project, CRISPR-Cas will be used to generate a new line of mammalian cells by inserting a fluorescent protein sequence (mNeonGreen) into the Notch1 sequence, to create cells with a Notch1-mNeonGreen fused protein. Three guide RNAs were designed to target the Notch1 sequence in the mammalian genome. The guide RNAs were packaged into circular pieces of DNA (plasmids) that also contained the Cas9 enzyme, creating a dual plasmid. In cells, Cas9 and the guide RNA can generate a dual plasmid complex that will target and cut the double strands of DNA that encodes the Notch1 protein to insert the mNeonGreen sequence. For future work, the dual plasmid needs to be combined with a plasmid that contains the mNeonGreen sequence, so it can be taken up by mammalian cells, potentially generating a new line of cells that express the Notch1-mNeonGreen fused protein.

Introduction

NOTCH SIGNALING PATHWAY AND ITS RECEPTOR NOTCH1

The Notch signaling pathway consists of four Notch proteins (Notch 1-4) that are important for the development of tissues, specifically the specialization of cells to form cell types that have particular functions in the body.⁹ In particular, Notch signaling plays a role in cell fate determination, cell growth, cell division, and cell maturation. This conserved pathway is present in metazoan animals, and it is one of the most important biological processes in multicellular development.

Notch1 is a transmembrane surface protein that has an extracellular (outside of the cell) domain and an intracellular (inside the cell) domain.⁹ The protein is considered transmembrane since a majority of the protein is embedded in the plasma membrane of cells.⁹ In general, receptor proteins have sites that are specific and receive signals from certain ligands (another type of protein) that can bind to it and send

the signal.⁵ If a ligand from one cell binds to the Notch1 receptor present on the adjacent cell, the Notch signaling pathway occurs due to cell-to-cell communication.^{1,9} The pathway determines the fate of a cell based on the physical interaction (cell-to-cell contact) it has with a neighboring cell through the Notch1 receptor and ligand.⁵

The mechanism of Notch signaling starts with a ligand from a signaling cell binding to the Notch1 receptor on the receiving cell (Figure 1).⁵ Due to the binding, the Notch1 transmembrane receptor protein is cut by proteases (enzymes that cut proteins) at the amino acid Valine1744.^{1,9,28} The cut generates a NICD (Notch Intracellular Domain) fragment, which travels from the cell plasma membrane to the nucleus, to interact with the nuclear protein CSL (Figure 1).²⁸ This interaction triggers the activation of target genes²⁸, like HEY1 (hairy/enhancer-of-split related with YRPW motif 1), which is a protein that positively regulates a tumor suppressor protein (p53).^{3,9}

Figure 1. Notch signaling pathway is involved in cell-to-cell communication and development. The Notch ligand binds to the Notch receptor and releases the NICD fragment. NICD then moves to the nucleus, which activates target genes due to its interaction with the CSL nuclear protein.²⁰

Since the Notch pathway plays an important role in cell death, malfunctions within this pathway has been linked to cancer.⁵ For example, low expression/transcription of HEY1 has been shown in breast cancer due to its mis-regulation of the tumor suppressor protein p53.⁹ The p53 protein regulates cell division by not allowing cells to grow and divide at a rapid pace or in an uncontrolled manner.⁹ Therefore, if HEY1 is inhibiting the expression of p53 protein, then cancerous cells will not be instructed to commit cell suicide.⁵ Therefore, if the p53 protein is mis-regulated, cells will be able to divide uncontrollably and cause cancer.⁵

CRISPR-CAS AND ITS NATURAL SYSTEM IN MICROBES

Microbes are defined as microorganisms that are often not seen with the naked eye. Microbes are widely known for their small size and ability to live wherever there is liquid water.¹ Microorganisms are present in the three branches of life, which include Archaea, Bacteria, and Eukarya.¹ However, microbes are further categorized as either eukaryotic or prokaryotic.² Eukaryotic microbes contain a nucleus and membrane-bound organelles like chloroplast, mitochondria, and the Golgi-apparatus.¹ Examples of eukaryotic microbes are yeast, microscopic algae, and protist. In contrast, prokaryotic microbes don't have a nucleus and lack membrane-bound organelles, making their cells much smaller in size in comparison to eukaryotic cells.¹ Archaea and bacteria are categorized as prokaryotes and through genome sequencing, it was revealed that there were arrays of DNA repeats present in their chromosomes.¹

The arrays of DNA repeats were later named CRISPRs (Clustered Regularly Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats), which are organized clusters of DNA sequences located next to the Cas-encoding genes on the chromosome, which plays a vital role in their immune system.¹ Prokaryotic microbes have DNA processing enzymes that are categorized as the Cas system, which will cut invading foreign DNA like viruses and place the foreign DNA within the organized clusters/CRISPRs.¹ The archived DNA that

is organized as CRISPR arrays are close to each other on the chromosome and contain short segments with inverted repeats, signifying a “bar code” that represents an exact encounter with foreign DNA.¹ Utilizing this analogy, each “bar code” represents each encounter the prokaryotic cell experiences with a specific piece of foreign DNA. CRISPR-Cas therefore functions as a memory system to archive previously encountered foreign DNA in a bacterial or archaeal chromosome so if the cell encounters the foreign DNA again, it will be immediately tagged and destroyed.¹ CRISPR-Cas plays a huge role in the speed of prokaryotic immunity by generating a memory system that will quickly target the foreign DNA upon re-exposure, limiting the damage caused by the invader to the host.⁴

The mechanism of CRISPR-Cas in providing immunity for prokaryotes begins with transcribing DNA into precursor RNA (pre-crRNA) that are complementary to the foreign DNA originally encountered in the cell (Figure 2).¹ Since the pre-crRNA has repeats, it forms a hairpin-like structure due to chemical bonding that are recognized by Cas enzymes and process the pre-crRNA into small CRISPR RNAs (crRNAs).¹ These crRNAs contain a tag that will bind to the previously encountered foreign DNA and target the DNA for destruction if that foreign DNA enters the cell again (Figure 2).¹ The CRISPR-Cas system is vital for immunity in prokaryotes and can be passed down to offspring since the CRISPR clusters are integrated into the chromosome, which is inherited.¹ If a cell contains CRISPR clusters that recognized multiple types of foreign DNA, then the progeny of that cell will also be immunized to the multiple types of previously encountered foreign DNA.¹ Therefore, daughter cells don’t need to encounter the same foreign DNA the mother cell encountered to gain immunity because immunity genes, in the form of CRISPR clusters, were passed onto their genome.¹

Figure 2. The figure above demonstrates how foreign DNA is cleaved by the Cas system and inserted into CRISPR clusters located on the chromosome of a prokaryote (bacteria or archaea).¹ For immunity, the CRISPR clusters are transcribed, and pre-crRNA binds to the Cas system to degrade foreign DNA once the crRNA has recognized it as foreign.¹

CRISPR-CAS SYSTEM AS A GENE EDITING TOOL

Genome editing is when multiple technologies are used by scientists to change an organism's DNA. Genome editing may involve adding, removing, or altering genes at certain locations in the genome, which is in the cell's nucleus.³ The editing of a mammalian genome has provided insight into treatment for genetic disease like sickle cell anemia, which causes red blood cells to become rigid, instead of round, due to a defect in the gene that encodes for hemoglobin.²⁶ Hemoglobin is a protein that contains iron and is vital for the transport of oxygen to tissues in red blood cells.²¹ Therefore, if the red blood cell is sickled-shaped, oxygen won't be delivered to tissues as quickly since it will have low affinity for the altered red blood cell. In December of 2023, the FDA approved CRISPR-based gene

therapy to treat patients with sickle cell anemia.^{25,30} Although CRISPR-Cas was originally found as part of the immune system of prokaryotes, the Cas proteins were engineered to utilize their activity for editing and treating sickle cell anemia. Cas proteins are enzymes that cut pieces of DNA¹, which allows the targeting and cutting of the gene of interest within the mammalian genome that causes hemoglobin to become sickled instead of round and flexible.^{2,3}

Although excitement within the scientific community was mostly due to the use of CRISPR-Cas to treat genetic diseases, CRISPR-Cas can also be used for other purposes. The CRISPR-Cas system has been utilized in the scientific community mostly for genome editing due to its speed and accuracy, which is hard to achieve in other genome editing methods.³ The popularity of using CRISPR-Cas has increased due to its ability to add or delete sequences that are located in a specific site in the genome, called the guide RNA sequence.⁶ For the best results, CRISPR-Cas is used to make small and targeted changes in DNA by utilizing guide RNA (or crRNA) to tell the complex where to cut and Cas9 enzymes that do the actual cutting (Figure 3).^{7,29} Allowing researches to edit DNA sequences can be used to track complex cellular process and /or discover the function of certain proteins when they're mutated.

The first step in utilizing CRISPR for gene editing is designing guide RNA sequences to bind to the target DNA sequence of interest by complementary base pairing and having the guide RNA form a complex with the Cas9 protein (Figure 3).^{7,29} For the guide RNA and Cas9 complex to bind to the target sequence, it must use the protospacer adjacent motif (PAM) sequence to find the correct location (Figure 3).²⁹ PAM is a short DNA sequence that follows the DNA region targeted for cleavage by the CRISPR-Cas9 system.⁷ After the Cas9 enzyme binds to guide RNA, creates a complex, and attaches to the genomic DNA, the Cas9 enzyme cuts both strands of DNA (Figure 3).^{7,29} The outcome of the complex binding and cutting both strands of DNA allows insertion of the programmed DNA.⁷ The programmed

DNA can be any sequence of interest, but for this project, the inserted DNA was the mNeonGreen fluorescent protein.

Figure 3. Cas9 protein is combined with the guide RNA to form a complex that will complementary base pair with the DNA sequence adjacent to the PAM (yellow) sequence.⁷ The complex will then cut DNA at a specific location in the genome and add the programmed DNA sequence.²⁹

Research Aims and Objective

In this project, the gene of interest was the Notch1 gene, which encodes for the Notch1 receptor protein.⁹ The objective of this project is to use CRISPR-Cas on human cells to insert a 711 base pair sequence, that encodes the mNeonGreen yellow-green fluorescent protein, into one of the natural Notch1 receptor exon to encode a Notch1-mNeonGreen fused protein. Previously, it has been difficult to

insert long pieces of DNA (around 10 kilobases) into the mammalian genome. Therefore, this project will insert a smaller DNA sequence that encodes the mNeonGreen protein, to generate the fused Notch1-mNeonGreen protein to be expressed in a mammalian cell. If the Notch1-mNeonGreen fused protein is expressed, the protein complex will glow bright yellow-green.²⁰ Specifically, if the fused protein is encoded, embedded in the cell membrane, and a ligand bound triggers the generation of the NICD fragment from the Notch1-mNeonGreen receptor, the NICD fragment will glow yellow-green. With the visualization of the NICD fragment, it can be tracked throughout the cytoplasm and in the nucleus in the gene-edited cell.²⁸ The overall goal would be to visualize the yellow-green glow within the nucleus of the mammalian cell since that is the endpoint for the Notch1 receptor in the signaling pathway.²⁰ The ability to localize and “follow” a protein within a mammalian cell can further my understanding of the Notch pathway and how it allows the growth of tissues in multicellular organisms.

In addition, understanding how the Notch signaling pathway works can be useful in addressing how mutations in the proteins that participate in the pathway can lead to uncontrolled cell division, like the mis-regulation of HEY1 transcription factor that is found in breast cancer.⁹ The main benefit in researching/investigating the Notch signaling pathway is to discover information that can aid in the treatment of cancer. The result of my study will provide a bigger picture of how to use CRISPR-Cas as a gene editing tool into investigating the Notch signaling pathway, which can be detected using a bright mNeonGreen protein that will fluoresce yellow-green if encoded with the Notch1 receptor, creating a Notch1-mNeonGreen fused protein.

Methods

GUIDE RNA DESIGN AND PREPARATION

The Notch1 sequence was inserted into Benchling¹⁵ and three guide RNAs (inserts) were designed to target the gene. To find where in the Notch1 gene to target, human (*Homo sapiens*) and rat

(*Rattus*) sequences for Notch1 gene was aligned to find a matching point. The matching point of the amino acids found in both sequences was the part of the Notch1 gene that will be targeted by CRISPR-Cas.

After receiving the three sets of oligonucleotides (forward and reverse primers) for each designed guide RNA, they were prepared by first rehydrating, then annealing the forward and reverse primers. For rehydration, the two tubes that contained the forward and reverse primers were vortexed and centrifuged for thirty seconds.¹⁷ Then, 100 microliters of tris EDTA was added to the two tubes.¹⁷ The tubes were incubated at room temperature for five minutes and then mixed briefly by vortex. To make a working solution of 10 micromolar from the 100 micromolar stock solution, 45 microliters of tris EDTA buffer and 5 microliters of the 100 micromolar stock solution was added to two new tubes (one for the reverse primer and another for the forward primer).¹⁷ The 100 micromolar of stock solution was stored at -20 degrees Celsius.¹⁷

The next step of the cloning process was to anneal the reverse and forward primers for all inserts designed and place the tubes into a Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) machine to select the T7 ENDO program, which includes heating to 90 degrees Celsius then slowly cooling in a heating block.¹⁷ In a PCR tube, 4 microliters of forward and 4 microliter of reverse guide RNA primers were added.¹⁷ Then, 1 microliter of 10x annealing buffer and 1 microliter of sterile nanopure water was added into the same tube.¹⁷ The PCR tube was placed into a T7 ENDO program in the PCR machine for 20 minutes to heat, then slowly cool, the reaction. The product was 4 picomoles per microliters of double stranded DNA that contains our forward and reverse primer bound/annealed to one another in a solution. To phosphorylate the 5' ends of the double stranded DNA, which will create a strong hydrogen bond between the two primers, 5 microliters of 4 picomoles per microliter of the double stranded oligonucleotide was added to another tube. In the same tube, 2 microliters of 10x Ligation buffer, 1

microliter of T4 polynucleotide kinase (PNK) enzyme, and 12 microliters of nanopure water was added. The tube was placed in a T7 ENDO program for about thirty minutes to heat the solution to 37 degrees Celsius, then to 75 degrees Celsius, to heat the inactivate T4 PNK enzyme. However, the insert was altered due to the bad T4 PNK enzyme used to phosphorylate the 5' ends of the insert in the first trial. To alter the 13 microliters of insert, 1.7 microliters of 10x ligation buffer, 1 microliter of the new T4 PNK enzyme, and 14.3 microliters of nanopure water was added to a tube. The total volume of the 1 picomole per microliter of the altered/new phosphorylated insert was 30 microliters.

PREPARATION OF pX330 VECTOR CONTAINING THE CAS9 ENZYME

pX330 vector is a DNA molecule, in the form of a plasmid, that is used as a vehicle to carry DNA sequences of interest.¹⁵ The pX330 vector contains a human U6 promoter, the sequence for the Cas9 enzyme, two Bbs1 cut sites for digestion, and an ampicillin resistant gene sequence (Figure 5).¹⁷ The plasmid was designed and ordered on Addgene.¹⁷

To prepare the pX330 vector, the first step was to digest and dephosphorylate the vector.¹⁷ To perform this, 2.2 microliters of 1,500 nanograms of pX330 vector, 2 microliters of 10x buffer G with BSA, 0.5 microliters of Fast Digest BbsI enzyme, 1 microliter of FAST alkaline phosphatase enzyme, and 14.3 microliters of nanopure water was added to a 1.5 milliliter tube for a total volume of 20 microliters. The solution was placed in a 37 degrees Celsius water bath for one hour. Then, to purify the DNA, a PCR clean up protocol was closely followed. To determine the yield of DNA in the purified vector solution, a Nanodrop spectrophotometer was utilized.¹⁷ A Nanodrop spectrophotometer allows the measuring of DNA concentrations in a sample and showing how pure the DNA is, denoted by a hill only around 260 nanometers.¹⁶ In addition, to verify the digestion of the plasmid, gel electrophoresis was conducted to compare the bands of the digested and undigested plasmids by creating an electric field to push DNA molecules through the gel by size.¹⁷

LIGATION OF GUIDE RNA INSERT AND pX330 VECTOR TO MAKE DUAL PLASMID

To combine the pX330 vector and guide RNA insert to create the dual plasmid, the components were ligated (combined) and transformed into competent bacterial cells that can take up DNA from the environment.¹⁷ Transformation is a way for bacterial cells to take up DNA from the environment if the bacterial cells are competent, which is categorized as horizontal gene transfer.¹⁸ The first step was to set up the ligation reaction with a control (plasmid only) and three different inserts, but the same vector, that are each a good potential candidate for targeting the Notch1 protein in the mammalian genome (guide RNA).¹⁷ The inserts used in the ligation reaction were diluted by adding 1 microliters of the new phosphorylated 30 microliter solution of insert and 19 microliters of nanopure water. The diluted insert was incubated overnight at 16 degrees Celsius.

Four reaction tubes were generated for the ligation reaction. The tubes were incubated for an hour at room temperature. To transform the bacterial cells, competent cells were gathered from a -85 degree Celsius freezer and quickly thawed in water. Four 13 milliliter tubes were labeled (as vector and insert #1, vector and insert #2, etc) and 45 microliters of competent bacterial cells and 5 microliters of each ligation reaction was added to their assigned/labeled tube. The four tubes were placed in ice for thirty minutes. After thirty minutes, the bacterial cells were heat shocked by adding the tubes for forty-five seconds into a 42-degree Celsius water bath and returned to ice for four minutes. Then, 400 microliters of super optimal broth with catabolite repression (SOC) were added to each of the four tubes. The tubes were incubated at 37-degree Celsius with constant shaking for thirty minutes. After thirty minutes, 100 microliters of solution from each of the 13 milliliter tubes were added onto their assigned Luria Broth (LB) agar plates with ampicillin (amp). Since the pX330 vector contained an ampicillin gene, the bacterial colonies grown on the plate will be ampicillin resistant while contaminating bacterial colonies will die. Sterile beads were used to spread the liquid evenly over the plates. The plates were

then incubated overnight at 37 degrees Celsius and the number of colonies for each plate were counted.¹⁷

To determine if the bacterial cells took up the insert and plasmid to make a ligated dual plasmid, a PCR reaction was conducted for five randomly selected bacterial colonies grown on each LB-amp plate.¹⁷ First, a bacterial colony was gathered from the LB-amp plate using a micropipette and placed in a tube that contained 40 microliters of nanopure water. Each bacterial colony derived (5 total for each plate) had their own tube and the colonies were mixed in the sterile water by resuspension. Then, a master mix was prepared by adding 0.7 microliters of 0.1 micro-molarity hU6F forward primer (promoter), 0.7 microliters of the 0.1 micro-molarity reverse primer for the guide RNA inserts, 35 microliters of 2x Dream Tag master mix containing dNTPs, Dream Taq, and green buffer, and 26.6 microliters of nanopure water to a tube in ice.¹⁷ In five additional separate tubes, 1 microliter of the template (containing the assigned colony and water) and 9 microliters of the master mix was added for a total volume of 10 microliters. To perform a negative control, one tube contained no template but 9 microliters of the master mix. Therefore, there were six total reactions occurring in six different tubes for each LB-amp plate.

The six tubes were placed in a PCR machine to run the PCR and amplify the DNA sequence of interest. After the PCR, the reactions were run on a gel for gel electrophoresis to see if the desired result of a 268 base pair band was derived.¹⁷

DUAL PLASMID EXTRACTION AND PURIFICATION FROM BACTERIAL CELLS

To extract and purify the dual plasmid containing the guide RNA insert and the Cas9 pX330 plasmid from bacterial cells, a ZymoPURE Plasmid Midiprep kit was utilized. A Nanodrop was utilized to make sure there was enough purified DNA extracted from the bacterial cells so the dual plasmid can

be used to transfect the human embryonic kidney cells 293 (HEK 293T)²⁵ cell line to verify whether the dual plasmid can target and cut the Notch1 gene in a T7 Endonuclease Assay.¹⁷

PRIMER TESTING FOR PCR AMPLIFICATION STEP IN T7 ENDONUCLEASE ASSAY

The T7 Endonuclease Assay will determine whether the Cas9 protein will cut the Notch1 gene, directed by the guide RNA, once the dual plasmid is transfected (taken up)^{26,27} in HEK 293T cells.¹⁰ However, the PCR primers utilized to amplify the mutated gene of interest, after the dual plasmid has cut the Notch1 gene in HEK 293T cells, needed to be tested by transfecting the guide RNA in the same line of cells. To transfect the HEK 293T, an old split of cells was dyed with Trypan blue and counted using a hemocytometer to verify that 7×10^5 cells can be plated in a 6 well dish. Once two wells were plated with 7×10^5 cells, they were incubated overnight to begin the transfection process. For transfecting cells in a 6 well plate, what's needed is 7×10^5 cells, 2 micrograms of the guide RNA, 4 microliters of the Turbofect transfection reagent, and 200 microliters of OPIMEM media. Therefore, the amounts were added in one well and the other well served as a control with no transfected guide RNA.

After two days of incubation, the DNA of the experimental and control HEK 293T cells were extracted by adding 1 milliliter of PBS to both wells and gathering a cell scraper to scrape the cells off the well. After, the liquid of cells was pipetted into a 1.5 milliliter microcentrifuge tube, they were centrifuged to acquire a pellet of cells, which represented the cell's DNA. However, the DNA needed to be purified to get rid of contaminants like proteins. Therefore, a Wizard Genomic DNA purification kit was used to purify the transfected and non-transfected DNA of HEK 293T cells. A Nanodrop spectrophotometer was used to determine the amount of purified DNA acquired from the transfected and non-transfected HEK 293T cells. In addition, the DNA was amplified in a PCR reaction and the results were run on a gel to make sure the guide RNA could be amplified by the forward and reverse primers, which should generate a band size of around 850 base pairs.

Results

GUDE RNA DESIGN AND PREPARATION

Guide RNAs were designed to target a specific location in the large Notch1 DNA sequence. In addition, an insertion site for mNeonGreen needed to be located within the same targeted Notch1 DNA sequence. To find the location to insert mNeonGreen, the lab had previous data of a successful insertion site for mNeonGreen in the Notch complementary DNA, which was in a plasmid instead of the mammalian genome. The previous insertion site of mNeonGreen was found after the glycine (G) amino acid on exon 28, which is about 765 base pairs upstream of the targeted guide RNA site (Figure 4).

To find the place in the Notch1 genome to target for the guide RNA, the matching point for the amino acids that encode the Notch1 gene was found in both human and rat sequences. The sequences were aligned on National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI)²¹ to find the matching point. The matching point was the amino acids leucine, lysine, proline, leucine, lysine, and asparagine (LKPLKN), which are the amino acids that encode the Notch1 protein in human and rat sequences. The sequence of amino acids was found at the end of exon 28 and the beginning of exon 29 (Figure 4). Therefore, the guide RNAs were designed to target the sequence after exon 28, since that is the non-coding sequence for Notch1 and won't affect the encoding of the gene to make the Notch1 protein (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Part of Notch1 DNA sequence that will be targeted by the guide RNAs (inserts) by complementary base pairing and the insertion site for mNeonGreen (after glycine). The inserts were designed to target after exon 28 but before exon 29 in the Notch1 gene, which are the non-coding domains of Notch1.

The ordered oligonucleotide forward and reverse primers for each guide RNA insert had a hydroxyl (OH) group on the 3' end of the DNA sequence. A polynucleotide kinase enzyme was utilized to add a phosphate group to the 5' ends of the primers, to create a hydrogen bond between the forward and reverse primers, generating an annealed product. The annealed product was successfully created, which was our prepared guide RNA insert.

PREPARATION OF pX330 PLASMID CONTAINING THE CAS9 ENZYME

The pX330 plasmid was purchased from Addgene¹⁴; it contains DNA sequences for the Cas9 protein, ampicillin resistant gene, human U6 (hU6) promoter, and two restriction sites for the BbsI enzyme to cut the vector and generate enough space to add the insert (Figure 5).¹⁷ The ampicillin resistant gene was included in the plasmid so bacteria that take up the DNA in transformation, when plated, can be detected on ampicillin plates. After cutting/digesting the pX330 vector with the BbsI enzyme, alkaline phosphatase enzyme was added to remove phosphate groups from the 5' end of the plasmid. This was done to leave OH groups on the 3' ends only, so the plasmid DNA doesn't create a phosphodiester bond to itself, which won't allow the insert to be ligated.

Figure 5. The plasmid map of the vector pX330. The vector contains an insertion site, where BbsI enzyme will cut the sequence twice, which is denoted by the red triangles. The guide RNA sequence is in the insert (bottom in blue), which will integrate into the vector pX330.¹⁷

The digestion of the pX330 vector by BbsI restriction enzymes was verified and detected by running a small sample with the alleged digested pX330 vector and non-digested pX330 vector in a gel for gel electrophoresis. The digested plasmid should generate a band that is slightly smaller than the control band, since the digested plasmid was cut, which was seen on the gel (Figure 6).¹⁵ A 1 kilobase plus DNA ladder was loaded in the first column to compare the size of the bands from the purified

digested plasmid to the undigested plasmid (Figure 6). Since the digested plasmid band was smaller than the control band, the pX330 vector was successfully digested (Figure 6). The digested plasmid creates enough “space” to add the guide RNA insert, generating a dual plasmid (Figure 9).

To determine the yield of cut vector DNA, a sample was read on a Nanodrop spectrophotometer. The concentration of vector DNA was 40.2 nanograms per microliters, which was enough DNA to generate a dual plasmid once the insert was ligated. In addition, the curve showed a peak at 260 nanometers, which is a sign that the DNA is of good quality and purity.¹⁸

Figure 6. Gel electrophoresis of the purified vector (middle) and the undigested plasmid (far right) used as a negative control. The band for the purified, digested vector is slanted and smaller than the band for the undigested plasmid. Since the bands aren't the same, the vector was successfully cut and digested by the BbsI enzyme.

LIGATION OF GUIDE RNA INSERT AND pX330 VECTOR TO MAKE DUAL PLASMID

Bacteria were used so they could take up the insert and digested pX330 vector in a process called transformation. Transformation allows the bacteria cells to take up foreign DNA from their environment and, with the use of DNA ligase, create a phosphodiester bond between the guide RNA insert and pX330 vector in a process called ligation. Ligation is the process of combining two DNA fragments (in this project, the guide RNA inserts and pX330 vector) with a phosphodiester bond.²⁵ The ligation of the guide RNA and pX330 vector generated the dual plasmid, which will be used to target and cut the Notch1 gene in HEK 293T cells.

To determine whether the competent bacterial cells took up the ligated vector and insert, 100 microliters of the experimental result was plated on a LB-amp plate. As a negative control, bacteria that took up the pX330 vector only (no guide RNA) were plated in LB-amp plates. When comparing the vector only plate to the plates that had the vector and insert, the vector and insert plates contained several more bacterial colonies (Figure 7). The goal was to see 10x more colonies on the plates that have the insert versus the plate that had no insert.¹⁷ Since more colonies were seen in the insert and vector plates, versus the vector only plates, the bacteria most likely took up both pieces of DNA and combined them in a ligation reaction (Figure 7).

Figure 7. LB-ampicillin (amp) plate with bacterial colonies and pX330 vector only (left). Three LB-amp plates, each with their unique guide RNA sequence in the insert and the same digested pX330 vector, plated with bacterial cells (right). Vector only plate had 5 colonies while the vector and insert plates had a range of 25 to 200 colonies.

To solidify the bacterial cells took up the insert and digested pX330 vector plated with them in ampicillin plates, five randomly selected bacterial colonies were PCR amplified for each plate. The PCR amplified product was run on a gel for gel electrophoresis to detect the sizes of DNA sequences. If the bacterial colonies took up the vector and insert to make a dual plasmid, then a band size of 260 base pairs should be seen (Figure 8). In four out of five bacterial colonies, selected from the LB-amp plate with one guide RNA and a digested pX330 vector, generated a band size of 260 base pairs (Figure 8). In another LB-amp plate with a different guide RNA plated with the same digested pX330 vector, two out of five bacterial colonies generated a band size of 260 base pairs (Figure 8). Since most of the bacterial colonies in both guide RNA plates combined with the same pX330 vector generated a 260 base pair band, the transformation and ligation reactions were successful. Therefore, the dual plasmid was made

in the bacterial cells and could be extracted from any chosen bacterial colony that generated a 260 base pair band.

pX330-43624

pX330-43655

Figure 8. Gel electrophoresis results for the ten bacterial colonies derived from two LB-amp plates (5 colonies from each plate), each with different guide RNAs but the same digested pX330 vector. The control has no template to PCR amplify, which contained the bacterial colony mixed with nanopure water.

A visual summary of the methods followed to create the dual plasmid by preparing the guide RNA insert and pX330 vector independently, then combining them together by a ligation reaction, is shown in figure nine.

Figure 9. Visual representation for the methods used to prepare the pX330 vector and insert separately, then combined/ligated to generate the dual plasmid that will bind and cut our Notch1 gene of interest.¹⁷

DUAL PLASMID EXTRACTION AND PURIFICATION FROM BACTERIAL CELLS

After the gel electrophoresis results verified that most bacterial colonies took up and combined the guide RNA insert and digested pX330 vector containing the Cas9 enzyme, the dual plasmid was extracted from bacterial cells. ZymPURE Plasmid Midiprep was utilized to extract and purify the dual plasmid from one bacterial colony that generated the 260 base pair band (Figure 8). The dual plasmid needed to be purified so it could be used in transfection experiments (the uptake of DNA in mammalian cells). To confirm the dual plasmid was extracted and purified, a small sample was placed on a Nanodrop spectrophotometer to make sure enough DNA (more than 100 nanograms per microliters) was extracted. The nanodrop readings revealed a high yield of DNA (342.3 nanograms per microliters)

within the purified plasmid from one bacterial colony. Therefore, the Plasmid Midiprep kit was successful in removing the dual plasmid from one bacterial colony and providing enough purified DNA for HEK 293T cells to be transfected with the dual plasmid in the T7 Endonuclease Assay.

PRIMER TESTING FOR PCR AMPLIFICATION STEP IN T7 ENDONUCLEASE ASSAY

The T7 Endonuclease 1 Assay is a mismatch detection assay that is used to evaluate the mutations made in the genome due to the dual plasmid.²⁶ If CRISPR-Cas was used to target the Notch1 gene by the guide RNA and cut the DNA sequences by the Cas9 enzyme,³ the modified locus could be confirmed by the endonuclease enzyme generating 580 base pair bands on a gel. Therefore, if the endonuclease enzyme was able to cut at the detected modified locus, then the dual plasmid was successful in detecting and cutting the Notch1 gene.

HEK 293T cells were transfected with the Notch1 guide RNA in pX330 vector. PCR amplification of the transfected and non-transfected DNA in HEK 293T cells was done to test the PCR primers of the guide RNA needed in the T7 Endonuclease Assay. After transfecting HEK 293T cells with the guide RNA, isolating the DNA, and purifying the DNA, the sample was run on a Nanodrop to verify enough DNA was extracted. Transfected cells had 302.3 nanograms per microliter of DNA while non-transfected cells contained 8.3 nanograms per microliter. However, the HEK 293T cell DNA (not transfected) was contained in a small area within the microcentrifuge tube, which wasn't pipetted into the Nanodrop. Therefore, the Nanodrop reading for control/non-transfected HEK 293T cells was inaccurate.

In addition, the sample was run on a gel to verify the PCR primers, to be used in the future for the PCR amplification step of the T7 Endonuclease Assay, worked (Figure 10). If the guide RNA primers were able to be amplified in the PCR reaction, then an 853 base pair band should be generated in the transfected HEK 293T cells. In transfected cells only, a 750 base pair band was generated, which

is close enough to the desired 853 base pair product to confirm the primers worked (Figure 10). In non-transfected cells, since they didn't have the guide RNA genomic DNA to be amplified by the guide RNA forward and reverse primers, the band size generated was around 90 base pairs (not shown). Therefore, the guide RNA PCR primers can be utilized in transfected cells for the PCR amplification step in the T7 Endonuclease Assay, which will eventually test whether the dual plasmid was able to target and cut the Notch1 gene. Due to time constraints, the T7 assay couldn't be performed to test whether the dual plasmid was able to generate a modified locus in the Notch1 gene in HEK 293T cells.

Figure 10. PCR amplification of the HEK 293T cells transfected with the guide RNA for the Notch1 gene (right). The 750 base pair band in transfected cells show the amplification of the forward and reverse primers for the guide RNA, which can be used in the PCR amplification step in the T7 Endonuclease Assay.

Discussion

The preparation of the guide RNA inserts and digesting the pX330 plasmid containing the Cas9 enzyme was done to generate a dual plasmid (Figure 9). The dual plasmid is one portion of utilizing CRISPR-Cas as a genome editing tool since it will target the Notch1 gene of interest and cut it. However, the purpose of cutting the Notch1 gene was to insert our programmed DNA, which was the mNeonGreen fluorescent protein sequence. Therefore, a targeting vector that contains the mNeonGreen sequence will need to be constructed.

Although the targeting vector wasn't constructed, it was designed. The targeting vector contained linkers and homology arms, along with the mNeonGreen sequence, to make sure the protein will fold correctly when it is encoded. In this project, the site to insert the mNeonGreen sequence was found to be after the glycine residue, which is about 765 base pairs upstream of the guide RNA target site (Figure 4). mNeonGreen will be inserted into the coding regions of the Notch1 gene, exon 28, to make sure the Notch1-mNeonGreen fused protein is encoded in mammalian cells.

Once the targeting vector that contains the mNeonGreen sequence is constructed, it can be transfected into HEK 293T cells, along with the dual plasmid. Transfection in HEK 293T cells with the dual plasmid and the targeting vector will allow the targeting, cutting, and insertion of the mNeonGreen sequence into the Notch1 gene, hopefully generating a new line of cells that encode the Notch1-mNeonGreen fused protein. However, the dual plasmid would need to be tested first to make sure the complex can target and cut the Notch1 gene. Therefore, the T7 Endonuclease assay would need to be conducted on HEK 293T cells (Figure 11).¹⁷ First, the targeted cells would need to be transfected with the dual plasmid and guide RNA primers would need to be used to PCR amplify the guide RNA in the PCR amplification step. The testing of guide RNA PCR primers for the guide RNA in the Notch1 gene

was performed and generated a close enough base pair band to conclude the PCR primers can be used for the T7 Endonuclease Assay (Figure 10).

Transfection of targeted cells with the dual plasmid could either include the modified locus in both strands of DNA, the modified locus in one strand of DNA, or have no modified locus in either strand of DNA (Figure 11). However, the T7 Endonuclease 1 enzyme will detect mismatches in double stranded DNA and cut the sequence, which can be detected by running a sample on a gel for gel electrophoresis. If the dual plasmid was able to target and cut the Notch1 gene to generate a modified/mutant locus, and the T7 Endonuclease 1 enzyme will cut the mismatches, then a band size of 580 base pairs should be seen on the gel.

Figure 11. Outline of the T7 Endonuclease assay utilized to test if CRISPR-Cas worked/targeted the Notch1 gene by the guide RNA, and cut the DNA sequence by the Cas9 enzyme, to generate a modified locus.

Due to time constraints, the T7 Endonuclease Assay couldn't be conducted. Although, the PCR primers of the guide RNA can be used in the PCR Amplification step in the assay due to successful generation of a 750 base pair band, which is close to the desired 853 base pair band (Figure 10). After the T7 assay successfully concludes that the dual plasmid was able to target and cut the Notch1 gene in HEK 293T cells, it can be used in a transfection experiment with the targeting vector, generating a new line of cells that encode the Notch1-mNeonGreen fused protein.

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